

Finding the Speed of Light From Gauss' Law and Special Relativity

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The speed of light is usually shown to be $1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$ where ϵ_0 and μ_0 are parameters from Maxwell's EM equations. Maxwell showed that one may write a wave equation for E (electric field) and a separate one for B (magnetic field) such that a speed = frequency * wavelength emerges, with speed = $1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$.

Here, we try to obtain the speed of light using Gauss' law in a rest frame, $\text{grad} \cdot \mathbf{E} = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \rho$ charge density and special relativity. We consider a charge Q at rest interacting with a test charge q (at rest) (both held in place) so that potential energy = $q \phi$ = type of rest mass. We call ϕ the electrostatic potential in the rest frame. We transform $(0, q \phi)$ to obtain $(g q v/b \phi, g \phi)$. We assume that one does not know that the velocity parameter in special relativity is c, and call it b instead. $g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$.

We argue that both $g v \phi$ and $g \phi$ should be related to force, possibly through d/dt partial and grad. This involves introducing a constant μ_0 so we define: $\mathbf{A} = (\mu_0 \epsilon_0) \mathbf{v} \phi$. The key to the argument is that one wishes to have an expression for E which uses $-\text{grad} \phi$, like in the rest case, but adds a piece, which makes the vector portion of E independent of g, because one should be able to write a usual vector (without g factors) for a moving charge.

These above ideas lead to $b = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$. Thus, the b (velocity constant) in the Lorentz transformation is $1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$ and experimental values for ϵ_0, μ_0 , show this equals the speed of light in a vacuum.

Lorentz Transformation For a Particle with Rest Mass

One may develop the Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass without any considerations of a photon or its speed c. In particular, one may argue that a particle with rest mass m_0 sitting at $x=0$ at t may be seen by a frame moving at a constant $-v$, or v . There are two frames which give the same speed, but only one $v=0$ frame.

As suggested in previous notes, we consider a product of the $-v$ and v results equalling a mo squared result. An equality is allowed, we argue, because one has the same physical situation whether it is viewed from a moving frame or not.

We suggest that in the moving frame, one sees a mass $m(|v|)$ and a flux mv or $-mv$. We look for a unitary transformation that gives such a result, namely, for $-v$:

$$\begin{aligned} |g \quad (v/b)g| & \quad ((1)) \quad \text{Here } g \text{ is some unknown function of } |v|. \\ | -g (v/b) \quad g | & \quad b \text{ is an unknown constant with velocity units.} \end{aligned}$$

We apply ((1)) to $(0, m_0)$ and ((1)) with $v \rightarrow -v$ to $(0, m_0)$ and take the usual dot product (no extra -1) and equate it to the dot product of $(0, m_0)$. This yields:

$$gg m_0 m_0 (1-vv/bb) = m_0 m_0 \quad \text{so} \quad g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb} \quad ((2))$$

Thus, one has a Lorentz transformation, which applies to energy (proportional to $(0, m_0)$), but there is an unknown constant b with units of velocity. We suggest that this Lorentz transformation also applies to (x, t) . One may see that for $x=0$, t , one has: $x' = -v t$ and $t' = \gamma t$ so that $x'/t' = -v$, the speed one should see in a frame moving with $-v$.

Lorentz Transformation Applied to an Electrostatic Situation

We next consider a charge Q at rest and fixed interacting with a test charge q , also fixed and at rest. The potential energy is $q \phi''(x'', t'')$. We call ϕ'' the potential in the rest frame and x'', t'' the spacetime variables in this frame. Explicitly, it is known from Gauss law: $\text{grad} \cdot \mathbf{E} = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \text{ charge density}$ and $\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad} \phi$ that:

$$\phi'' = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) 1/\sqrt{x''^2 + y''^2 + z''^2} \quad ((3))$$

We argue that $q \phi''$ should transform via a Lorentz transformation. Thus:

$$(0 \ q \ \phi'') \longrightarrow (q \ g \ v \ \phi'', \ g \ \phi'') \quad ((4)) \quad \text{Here we use } v = (v, 0, 0)$$

As seen in the moving frame, there is a momentum vector $g \ v \ \phi''$ and $g \ \phi''$. One may rewrite x'', t'' in terms of the x, t moving frame variables i.e.

$$X'' \rightarrow \gamma(x - vt) \quad y'' \rightarrow y \quad z'' \rightarrow z \quad ((5))$$

If $-\text{grad} \phi''$ is \mathbf{E} ($q\mathbf{E}$ is force) in the rest frame, both $g \ \phi''$ and $g \ v \ \phi''$ should be associated with force. The question to determine is exactly how. We note that $g \ v \ \phi''$ is a vector and so one cannot simply take grad of it. One wishes to have a vector force. Two possibilities are:

$$-d/dt \ g \ v \ \phi'' \quad \text{and} \quad v_1 \times (\text{grad} \times g \ v \ \phi'') \quad ((6))$$

Here v_1 is the velocity of a charge interacting with the moving Q . Given that $-\text{grad}$ in the rest frame is linear, one only wants linear operators in the moving. A third possibility is $v \cdot (\text{grad} \cdot v \ g \ \phi'')$. (The Lorentz gauge shows that this is equivalent to $-d \phi''/dt$ partial and so is not a new piece. The Lorentz gauge is: $d \phi''/dt + \text{grad} \cdot (\mathbf{C} \ v \ \phi'') = 0$ which is type of continuity equation.)

An issue with units, however, ensues. Grad acting on ϕ'' multiplied by q should have force units, so the second term in ((6)) requires a constant u_0 to allow for force units. We define:

$$\mathbf{A} = (u_0 \epsilon_0) \ g \ v \ \phi'' \quad ((7)) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{B} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{A} \quad \text{such that} \quad q \ \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} \quad \text{yields a special force.}$$

This force is called the magnetic force and has no x component for the constantly moving Q situation.

So far no progress has been made in determining the value of b , the constant used in the Lorentz transformation. In fact, u_0 has been introduced in such a way as to absorb b . A key point is that u_0 and e_0 are both measurable values. The B field, as noted, only acts perpendicular to v . If one had a current with net charge 0 (i.e. electrons moving in a wire), there would be no E field and one could simply measure the B field and hence u_0 . The value of e_0 is already found in the electrostatic rest frame.

In order to find b , we make the following suggestion. From ((6)), there are two force pieces. One has been found to be a B field linked with a force perpendicular to motion.

In the rest frame $-\text{grad } \phi$ is E. If one simply uses $-\text{grad } \phi$ in the moving frame, one finds:

$$-\text{grad } \phi = -\text{grad } \phi / \sqrt{(x-vt)^2 + y^2 + z^2} = -g \{ g(x-vt) e(i) + y e(j) + z e(k) / \sqrt{(x-vt)^2 + y^2 + z^2} \} \quad ((8))$$

Here $e(i)$ is a unit vector in the i -direction.

The key argument we make is that one should not have a vector containing g in E. E in the moving frame represents force in the direction $(x-vt) e(i) + y e(j) + z e(k)$. There should be no g modifying the $e(i)$ component. Thus, an extra piece needs to be added to $-\text{grad } \phi$ in the moving frame. We consider the candidate:

$$-d/dt A \text{ partial} \quad ((9))$$

We use A, containing u_0 , because this was used in $B = \text{grad } \times A$. We argue that this should link b (constant velocity unit from the Lorentz transformation to e_0, u_0). To see this, consider:

$$A = e(i) g v \phi (u_0 e_0) \text{ so } ((9)) = g v v (x-vt) e(i) / \{ g(x-vt) e(i) + y e(j) + z e(k) / \sqrt{(x-vt)^2 + y^2 + z^2} \} \quad ((10))$$

Combining this with $-\text{grad } \phi$, one has:

$$e(i) g (-1 + v v e_0 u_0) \quad ((11)) \text{ where } g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$$

$$\text{Thus, } e_0 u_0 = 1/bb \text{ and } b = 1/\sqrt{e_0 u_0} \quad ((12))$$

Experimentally, one may find that $1/\sqrt{e_0 u_0}$ equals the speed of light in a vacuum, and so b seems to be the speed of light in a vacuum.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may find the speed of light in a vacuum $= 1/\sqrt{e_0 u_0}$, where e_0, u_0 are the EM parameters, without using a wave-equation for E and B and arguing that $1/\sqrt{e_0 u_0} = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$. We suggest that this same result may be obtained

without using a wave-equation, but only Gauss' law and considerations of a Lorentz transformation. We develop the Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass and introduce a constant b with units of velocity, so v/b is dimensionless. This leads to the problem that b is unknown. We then consider the potential energy of a charge Q at rest interacting with a charge q also at rest. The potential energy $q\phi$ is like rest mass and should transfer via a Lorentz transformation. Thus $(0, q\phi) \rightarrow (q\gamma v\phi, q\gamma\phi)$. We argue that both $q\phi$ and the vector $q\gamma v\phi$ should be linked with force if one takes linear derivatives d/dt partial, grad partial. We define: $A = \gamma v (\epsilon_0 \epsilon_0) \phi$ so that it has appropriate units if one creates a force using $v \times (\text{grad} \times A)$. Here v is the velocity of a test charge. So far, there is no information about b . We argue that in the moving frame, $-\text{grad} q\phi$ is no longer E because the vector piece is: $(\gamma \frac{d}{dt} (x-vt), y, z)$. A vector in the moving frame should be $(\frac{d}{dt} (x-vt), y, z)$. An extra piece of E field is needed to achieve this and we show that $-\frac{dA}{dt}$ partial satisfies this requirement if: $1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} = b$. Thus, b is found in terms of electromagnetic parameters. Experimentally, $1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$ yields the speed of light in a vacuum and so should be this value.